

SOIL PROPERTIES OF NEWLY IRRIGATED SEROZEM-MEADOW SOILS BY ELEVATION LEVEL BASED ON GAT TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation: Ushbu maqolada Jizzax viloyati hududida tarqalgan yangidan sug'oriladigan bo'z-o'tloqi tuproqlarning gumus, harakatchan fosfor, almashinuvchi kaliy, fizik loy, quruq qoldiq hamda hajm og'irligi ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha ularning tuproqlardagi miqdorlarini GIS texnologiyasidan foydalangan holda turli balandliklari bo'yicha malumotlar qayt etilgan.

This article presents data on the content of humus, mobile phosphorus, exchangeable potassium, physical clay, dry residue, bulk density of newly irrigated serozem-meadow soils distributed in the Jizzakh region at different altitudes using GIS technology.

Key words: GIS technologies, humus, mobile phosphorus, exchangeable potassium, mechanical composition, map, elevation, serozem-meadow soil.

Introduction. To date, the main directions of application of GIS technologies in the world have been established, which also include accurate assessment of the situation and rapid response. Currently, GIS technologies are used in a number of areas. In particular, they are widely used in public services, emergency services, medicine, ecology, education and many other areas[1].

Geographic information technology greatly assists in dealing with spatial data and complex interactions in state building, in land management, urban and rural planning, transport management, and environmental management[2].

Research object and methods. The newly irrigated serozem-meadow soils of the “Kazakhstan” massif of the Arnasay district of the Jizzakh region were selected as the object of the study. The study was carried out based on the instructions for conducting soil surveys and compiling soil maps for maintaining the state land cadastre [3] and generally accepted methods. General chemical and physicochemical soil analyses were performed according to generally accepted methods based on the manuals of Ye.V. Arinushkina [4]. Analysis based on geographic information systems was performed using the ArcGIS program and its Geostatistical Analyst modules.

Research results and their analysis. The humus content of the study area was determined by altitude and is described as follows. In particular, the humus content in low-altitude irrigated areas (250-259 m) ranged from 178,4 ha (16,8%), (0,81-1,2%) to 699,8 ha (65,7%). At irrigated medium altitudes (259-268 m), the amount of humus decreased sharply, only in the range of (0,4-0,8%) it amounted to 65,8 ha, or (6,2%), and in the range of (0,81-1,2%) it amounted to 120,6 ha, or (11,3%).

Picture-1

Picture-1. Dynamics of changes in soil properties at different altitudes of irrigated soils in the selected reference area.

The exchangeable potassium plant was found to occupy 875.54 ha (82.2%) of the land area in this region, mainly at low altitudes (250-259 m), with an average content of 201-300 mg/kg. At the highest altitudes (259-268 m), the level of potassium supply is much lower, with only 189,06 ha (17,8%) of the land area having an average of 201-300 mg/kg.

Picture-2

Picture-2. Map of the elevation of the "Kazakhstan" massif above sea level.

Mobile phosphorus, on the other hand, is found at low altitudes (250-259 m) in 319,2 ha (30,0%) of the land with a phosphorus index of 0-15 mg/kg, and in 559,6 ha (52,6%) with an average index of 16-30 mg/kg. At the highest altitudes (259-268 m), the amount of phosphorus decreases significantly, only 55,7 ha (5,2%) of the land areas with an average index of 0-15 mg/kg, and 130,1 ha (12,2%) of the land areas with an average index of 16-30 mg/kg. The mechanical composition of the soil at these low altitudes (250-259 m) where the physical clay content is 166,2 ha (15,6%), sand (5-10%), sandy loam (10-20%) 170,9 ha (16,1%), light loam (20-30%) soils predominate, accounting for 479,0 ha (45,0%). Medium loam (30-40%) areas accounted for 62,4 ha (5,9%).

At medium altitudes (259-268 m), it was found that areas with sand (5-10%) accounted for 31,6 ha (3,0%), sandy loam (10-20%) accounted for 68,8 ha (6,5%), light loam (20-30%) soils accounted for 80,5 ha (7,6%), and medium loam (30-45%) soils accounted for 5,2 ha (2,8%). The dry residue content at low altitudes (250-259 m) was 0,13-0,28% on 517,84 ha (48,6%), 0,29-0,43% on 120,0 ha (11,3%), and 0,44-0,59% on 240,6 ha (22,6%). At high altitudes (259-268 m), the dry residue content decreased: only 0,13-0,28% on 52,74 ha (5,0%), 0,29-0,43% on 29,9 ha (2,8%), and 0,44-0,59% on 103,44 ha (9,7%). Bulk density At low (250-259 m) elevations where irrigated soils are located, 295,0 ha (27,7%) have soil bulk density in the range of 1,20-1,30 g/cm³, and 59,4 ha (5,6%) have soil bulk density in the range of 1,30-1,40 g/cm³. At high (259-268 m) elevations, 583,4 ha (54,8%) have soil bulk density in the range of 1,20-1,30 g/cm³, and 126,8 ha (11,9%) have soil bulk density in the range of 1,30-1,40 g/cm³.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it is worth noting that, according to the results of the study, it was found that in the studied area, areas belonging to the soil humus (0,81-1,2%) group occupied large areas at low altitudes (250-259 m). In the middle areas, areas with humus (0,81-1,2%) occupied relatively small areas at low altitudes. Exchangeable potassium, on the other hand, accounted for an average of 201-300 mg/kg of supply at low altitudes (250-259 m). At high altitudes (259-268 m), this indicator decreased somewhat.

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